

User Experience Research Report 2023

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RESEARCH GOALS AND METHODOLOGY

Research goals

The VU RDM support has changed dramatically over the last three years, which affected both the staff and the researchers alike. The current research is a re-run of the user research done in 2020 with the main focus of understanding the progress being made over the last three years. However, this time the research includes two perspectives: the one of researchers and the one of the RDM support staff, covering representatives of the Library, Faculties, and IT.

The goal of the research is to find answers to the questions below.

To properly compare the situation, the questions addressed to researchers stayed the same.

- How do researchers think about data management?
- How do researchers go about finding support for their data management practices?
- What are the obstacles the researchers face when finding such support?
- What do researchers wish they had in terms of RDM support?

The questions addressed to the staff were structured around the first four questions below. During the interviews with the staff members, it became evident that another, fifth area (not quite a question) of investigation should be added.

- What does RDM staff think of the RDM service at the VU?
- How has the development of the NeRDS changed the professional life of the RDM support staff?
- What are the challenges the staff face?
- What do the RDM support staff need more support with?
- The birth of the new RDM staff member.

Methodology

This research report is based on the 18 in-depth anonymous user interviews conducted online via Zoom. The interviews were approximately 60 minutes long. 9 users are researchers of VU Amsterdam University. 6 people have used RDM Support services before, and 3 people have not. Interviewees are from various faculties and have been with the University for 1-5 years. The other 9 users interviewed are RDM support staff members. Four of them were appointed into their roles a few months prior to the interviews, others have experience ranging from 3 to 5+ years.

SUMMARY OF KEY FINDINGS

RDM IN THE EYES OF THE STAFF MEMBERS

Enhancing RDM support at VU

VU's RDM support is growing, with more Data Coordinators and Data Stewards now available across the VU. New members of the RDM support community bring enthusiasm, tailoring their approaches to diverse RDM practices across faculties. Experienced staff feel RDM support is strengthening.

Courses such as 'How to write a DMP' provide a foundation for understanding RDM queries and increasing familiarity with the field. There is also more information available online, some Data Stewards confidently refer researcher to particular websites.

RDM support staff notices the shifting nature of researchers' inquiries in RDM. For example, new tools and developments, like Yoda, spark increased questions over the last year, while external factors like GDPR have previously influenced the focus of discussions when this topic was new. There is a noticeable increase in researchers' awareness of RDM tools and practices, as demonstrated by their tendency to ask more specific questions. RDM support is evolving, and it shows in both: queries from researchers and solutions provided by staff.

The staff believes that the Rresearchers are increasingly aware of the importance of RDM, and their expectations continue to rise. Sometimes the RDM support staff is challenged with a delicate balance between minimizing risk and enabling researchers to achieve their needs, as overly stringent processes might push researchers to adopt riskier alternatives like Dropbox for storing data.

The birth of a new RDM staff member

It seems that the VU was not prepared to have that many newly appointed members of the RDM community. Practical steps like proper introduction to the role as well as introduction to the tools require attention. In addition, there is also no recommendation on how the new staff should introduce themselves to the researchers and make them aware of an RDM person being present in a department.

However, new staff members, despite lacking formal introductions to their roles as Data Stewards and Data Coordinators, demonstrate remarkable drive and initiative. They swiftly delve into understanding researchers' RDM awareness and practices, often relying on their own research and colleagues' experiences.

New staff' adaptation to faculties' diverse RDM awareness involves varied approaches, with questionnaire surveys being a common practice. In some cases, staff may focus on storage-related questions when creating a survey, neglecting to consider RDM as a whole and deviating from a comprehensive approach to the research data cycle.

Community and Network

Various meetings for Data Coordinators and Data Stewards, whether at the faculty or broader levels, play a vital role. They help share insights about RDM roles and best practices, allowing members to learn from each other and improve their RDM approaches. Staff uses the words “community” and “network” interchangeably, thinking about meetings and a sense of community immediately when asked about the network of RDM staff.

With the development of the NeRDS Data Stewards as well as the RDM library team are seeing positive changes:

- Improved knowledge-sharing channels and practices;
- Stronger collaboration between departments, and more direct support for researchers;
- Further fostering a sense of trust and RDM community at VU.

However, not everyone associates themselves with being part of the network or believes the NeRDS impacts their job to some extent.

Challenges mentioned by staff

Both new and experienced staff members are anticipating more queries from the researchers as RDM culture is becoming more prominent at the VU. More experienced staff members highlight that there should be clearer expectations that Data Stewards are not wizards. There is a need to set clear expectations about the time required to understand and assist with researchers' projects, even when this assistance is as straightforward as commenting on a DMP.

Experienced faculty staff members note that they often encounter conflicts of interest with the library, IT department, and Legal department when assisting researchers with complex inquiries. Navigating these challenges requires more support and cooperation.

At times, RDM support information online is confusing even for the RDM staff, not to mention researchers. Particular areas for improvement are the storage finder tool, webpages on the “How to write a DMP” course and specific information on various new tools across multiple websites.

Some new and experienced data stewards mention that with the development of the NeRDS, they are not sure where their responsibilities end and NeRDS support begins.

Good to have for staff

Although being full of enthusiasm and eager to deliver results, the new staff members haven't had a proper introduction to the role, and this is a gap that needs closing. They do not talk about it explicitly, but they are often unsure of the scope of their responsibilities, the amount of workload they might be having in the future, and, more importantly, the full collection of tools and services available at the VU.

Due to the nature of the RDM service being re-active, RDM support staff doesn't receive regular feedback on their work from researchers. Yet, having a better idea of what worked and what didn't not only increases confidence when giving advice but also may save time in the future when RDM staff encounters similar issues.

Ideally, RDM support staff prefers early notification of upcoming complex research projects to adequately assist researchers in finding optimal RDM solutions or start cooperation with various departments.

The staff members expressed a desire for NeRDS to enhance support for major projects, akin to the presence of project managers in other faculties. In addition, the staff expressed the need for NeRDS to take ownership of crucial issues, such as complicated questions with multiple stakeholders like privacy and IT involved, where some Data Stewards feel somewhat isolated.

RDM IN THE EYES OF THE RESEARCHERS

How do researchers think about data management?

Compared to 2020, it is still a common practice to think about RDM as steps you may need to take to make sure your data is stored and archived safely. However, now there is a bit more talk about how RDM is connected to the integrity of and impact of the research. In this sense, those who know about RDM, think about RDM more holistically. However, it is still difficult for them to describe what they mean by good research data management.

Compared to 2020, when researchers would discover the RDM support available mostly by chance or when having to write a DMP for the grant, there is now a greater diversity of sources of learning. Some encounter RDM during Masters' courses pre-PhD, while others via emails, newsletters, VU events and departmental meetings. Those who are not obligated to complete the DMP course often rely on the advice of their colleagues or supervisors.

Similarly to 2020, DMP remains a vital introductory tool for researchers. DMP writers find the course incredibly valuable as it helps them gain a stronger understanding of the entire research data management cycle. However, those starting to write DMP later in their research, may find it unproductive. Individuals completing their PhDs without being exposed to Data Management Plans remain unaware of their purpose and continue using their existing methods.

While researchers strive to answer DMP questions comprehensively, they doubt the fact they can fully adhere to their plan. On the other hand, some people see broader implications of DMP, such as using this document to introduce established RDM practices to new researchers joining their projects. Such a realisation among researchers has not been seen in 2020.

How do researchers find support for their data management practices?

In contrast to 2020, when researchers didn't make good use of the information available online, this time it is often mentioned that websites are useful. They offer clear and basic support to understand not only what RDM is and how to approach it, but also to demonstrate the available support tools.

In contrast to 2020, when researchers frequently discovered RDM support accidentally or through word of mouth, there has been a significant change in 2023: the majority of interviewed researchers are aware of the departmental RDM support. However, not all engage with Data Stewards or Data Coordinators. Some only ask for help with tough questions, while others stick with the already familiar person for advice.

Experience seems to help a lot. Experienced staff view RDM as an integrated part of the research process not as a burden. They also now engage more in collaborative discussions with colleagues for quick RDM queries, a shift from 2020 when simple questions were considered as something that should be figured out by a researcher themselves, and such conversations were not mentioned.

Obstacles researchers face using RDM services.

Researchers continue to prioritise solving RDM-related questions only as they arise, much like in 2020. Across different levels of experience, from PhD candidates to experienced assistant professors, RDM-related concerns are not typically a cause for worry unless they are urgent.

The importance of time remains constant for researchers, as seen in 2023 and previous years. When individuals have settled into a particular workflow or are reliant on specific tools, it can be tough to change their practices, even if they acknowledge that their current practices may not be the most suitable. In previous years, people were primarily frustrated with having to adapt to new rules and tools during periods of change. However, in 2023, the main source of frustration has shifted towards finding more efficient storage solutions.

People who are not required to handle sensitive information and have progressed far in their research or doctoral studies are comfortable keep using the storage that is not perfect. The desire for better options is met with annoyance when one is compelled to transfer their data. Nonetheless, on the whole, there is a reduced level of difficulty in adjusting practices, perhaps because of early exposure to suitable tools and RDM protocols.

It can be challenging to complete required RDM-related courses due to unclear schedules and communication. The task of figuring out schedules and signing up is using up valuable time that could be spent on research. While some mandatory courses do cover essential topics such as scientific integrity, there have been concerns about their ability to sufficiently engage participants. Researchers also desire more practical examples, especially on what to avoid and why, alongside best practices learned in the DMP course.

Decision-making tools, available online, such as storage finder or data classification tool are sometimes confusing and frustrating for researchers. Although they appreciate the addition of a

storage finder tool, they feel that the provided information is not enough to make an informed decision.

Many people struggle with figuring out who to reach out to for assistance with data management systems, which is another obstacle that has been mentioned.

What do researchers wish to receive from RDM support?

There is a unanimous sentiment among researchers for earlier exposure to RDM practices.

Early completion of an RDM course has proven to be incredibly valuable for mid-PhD candidates, enabling them to efficiently handle research data and encouraging them to embrace the ideals of Open Science. Associate professors echo their researchers' sentiments, highlighting the challenge faced by those who encounter DMP or Research Integrity courses late in their PhD journey, underscoring the importance of timely engagement in these practices.

Similar to 2020, supervisors remain vital for researchers. Yet now there's a stronger desire for supervisors and PI's recognition of RDM's importance. To successfully implement RDM practices, adhere to FAIR principles, and utilize the Open Science Framework for paper publication, it is important to have the support, encouragement, and acknowledgement of supervisors or PIs.

The RDM community offers broad support, including events and courses, but overlooks certain topics. As an illustration, the latest AI advancements have caused quite a stir in academia. Yet, the RDM staff's failure to proactively communicate about them brings to light a certain disconnect between researchers and RDM support in navigating these innovations.

ANSWERING RESEARCH QUESTIONS

PART 1. STAFF' PERSPECTIVE

1. Enhancing RDM support at VU

a) RDM support is expanding

Compared to 2020, there are more staff members, who are responsible for the RDM support at the VU. Most notably, these are faculty data coordinators and data stewards.

The newly appointed staff members seem to start with a lot of enthusiasm and ideas. They organise their work depending on the current status of the RDM practices at their faculties and departments. They often find that the state of RDM varies greatly not just from faculty to faculty but also from department to department. In their roles as Data Stewards and Data Coordinators, they recognise the importance of RDM and enthusiastically try to make the practices of RDM better.

"We started to look into this whole thing called research data management not so long ago. In our department, people have not taking so much care about their research data very well. So there is a lot of work to do for us."

More experienced staff members note that in their view, the RDM support across the VU is getting stronger.

"I think the information that we provide is now a little bit better organized. I hope it is also a bit more findable."

"We have better solutions. For example, we have Yoda now. <...> So now we can really say, Okay, we have a policy, this is what we expect from researchers, and here are the tools to do that. And I think that really improved the whole system, similar to storage during research. So yeah, it was really difficult to give advice previously, because for some types of research, or for some types of data, there was just no good solution. And now we have something to offer, or we have various things to offer actually."

"I'm pretty sure that most people are aware of the FAIR principles because otherwise, you don't get any papers published these days."

However, not everyone shares this enthusiasm. Some experienced staff members recognise that there is a lot of work that needs to be done:

"I think that we have to be realistic and say, not that many people are aware [of all the tools and solutions we offer]. And the reason I'm saying that is sometimes I am invited to come and give a presentation at the department. <...> And then it turns out that even the people who have

found me, are blissfully unaware of most of the tools, and also of lots of regulations that the university has.”

“Currently, I think [RDM awareness] depends a lot on the program [researchers] are in or on their project. In our department “How to write a DMP” course is obligatory, and researchers need to take it, and this is how they learn the basics of RDM. But it’s not like this in other faculties, so maybe [researchers on those faculties] don’t really care.”

b) The basic questions of RDM are covered by the “How to write a DMP” course and the information available online.

It seems certain, however, that the level of awareness of RDM has risen in general, and especially at those faculties where “How to write a DMP” is a compulsory course. DMP has been proven to provide a solid foundation for the understanding of RDM and to cover basic questions.

“I think that the DMP course really helps. It makes the students think carefully about everything they do. I remember when I started here, during my bachelor's and master's we didn't learn anything about how to store data, and we never really realised the relevance of that. But it's different now. They need to think about [RDM], and they also know that they can ask me if they need help.”

“I think I get more specific questions now. I started working [in this field at the VU] when there wasn't much available for the researchers. No tools, like we have today. So there weren't many questions. But now we have the DMP course, and they need to apply for grants, so they need to find a storage and they need to know about FAIR principles.”

“Now we get more technical questions. There are more things on FAIR data, more things on open science, and more questions on those sorts of things. But there's a general evolution with people now aware that these are important things and necessary. In terms of FAIR data, far more people are asking about it.”

“When someone comes to me, it is one of the first questions I ask. Have you written the DMP yet? Are you planning on writing it? It is very good guidance and helps you to think about what you are going to do with the data. Many questions get answered just by writing a DMP.”

The information on RDM available on various VU websites also covers basic questions. Some RDM staff simply directs researchers to a particular website or use the information to answer their question:

“There's now more information on the basics of the RDM available through the network's efforts. And because of that, there's a lot of stuff I can use as a reference and to save myself time. I can say [to a researcher]: “I think this might be helpful for read-through. And then let's discuss your problem.” And then most the time they've got an idea of what they could do, or a better idea of what's at least available, and then we can discuss more specific or more complicated problems.”

“Sometimes I point them to the LibGuide and say that the answer is there. Because I used it myself a lot.”

c) The changes in questions and trends aren't definitive.

Based on the interviews, there is a variety of opinions about what sort of questions are coming from the researchers. New developments, like Yoda, spark increased inquiries, while external factors like GDPR have previously influenced the focus of discussions. There's a sense of rising awareness among researchers, reflected in more targeted and informed queries. Moreover, there's an observation that it's not just the questions but the solutions offered that are undergoing notable changes in RDM support.

"It's hard to tell [if there are trends in questions coming from researchers], as I've recently joined. But I hear a lot of discussion about storage, so maybe that's the core of the RDM for the researchers."

"The questions change when we have new things to offer for researchers. With Yoda, for example, we had many questions. And because it's new, people want to know more."

"Yes, there are of course changes. Sometimes it's not even dictated by the VU. A few years ago, for example, everyone was talking about GDPR. "

"I am not directly involved in answering questions, but from what I can see, it seems pretty much that we are still dealing with a lot of the same concerns and questions."

"I have the feeling that the level of awareness at least is higher than a few years ago. So the types of questions that come to us are a bit more like the researchers know better how to ask that question. Like, what is the relevant thing to ask for? That's my feeling."

"Sometimes I think can almost tell by the question if [researchers] even know about what DMP is or not."

"I think it's not so much questions, it's the solutions that we offer - this is what is changing."

d) With great power comes great responsibility

As the support is expanding and new solutions are offered, researchers are becoming more aware of the need and ability to practice good RDM. At times, they are becoming more demanding.

Sometimes the RDM support staff is challenged with a delicate balance between minimizing risk and enabling researchers to achieve their needs, as overly stringent processes might push researchers to adopt riskier alternatives like Dropbox for storing data.

The emphasis here lies in raising awareness rather than policing, acknowledging the trade-offs between complying with protocols and meeting researchers' urgent needs, often constrained by time and administrative processes.

"I think we will see more of these complicated questions in the future. And this is also something that we are working on to prepare for. Because of the way the research is moving now, people will need to use more digital tools, and those tools will probably be more

complicated.”

“Sometimes it is just like the flu. If we're going to achieve zero risk, then we should just stop doing research. So that's a bit of a complexity [in our work] of trying to find a way to minimize risk. But still allow researchers to do their work. Because my big concern is researchers are going to do their work one way or another. And if we keep making it so hard for them to do their jobs, and achieve, like 0.00001% risk, then they'll get frustrated and just use like Dropbox, which would be way worse.”

“We shouldn't police, we should make people aware so that they do it naturally. But it's always weighing options like time, effort, money, people. Sometimes they need a storage, but they need to start next month of whatever. Going through all the hoops at VU can take a bit, which is not within their timeframe. And we can make a recommendation like “don't go there, don't use that”. But some people definitely will be like I'm not going to wait, I need to do this.”

2. The birth of a new RDM staff member

Although there are many more RDM support staff at the VU, and they form strong connections with each other to support researchers, it seems that the VU was not prepared to have that many newly appointed members of the RDM community. Practical steps like proper introduction to the role as well as introduction to the tools require attention.

a) Challenges in Onboarding

New staff members face challenges when they start their job as Data Stewards. Their first challenge is little to no introduction to the role.

“I'm still trying to figure out what to do [with my role], but I think there's a lot of people that really don't know exactly what the purpose is and how far we want to take this.”

There was one member of the RDM community who was even surprised to find themselves being a Data Steward. This is how they describe the experience:

“I recently realized that I've also taken on a Data Steward role. <...> I only found out about the fact that I am a Data Steward about a week ago. I talked to my colleague and [offered help with DMPs], but I did not understand that this made me a Data Steward in the eyes of other people. So I'm officially at some level now being considered a Data Steward for our faculty.”

b) Guidance on how to approach researchers

It seems that there is a gap in the expected role of data coordinators in introducing researchers to RDM services. Most new members of RDM support staff proactively introduce themselves. Some rely on personal emails to introduce their roles, pointing out a potential lack of visibility for their positions on departmental websites or internal platforms compared to other roles.

"It was supposed to be done via coordinators, via RDM Coordinator. Data coordinators are supposed to introduce researchers to RDM services. They're supposed to be the person that can point, if not solve the problem, but at least point them in some direction."

"We have things where they will give lectures and different talks with different group meetings, and we actively work with the audience coordinator at the departmental level, yes, but not at the faculty level."

"I simply send an email out, saying who I am and what I will be doing. I don't think that my role is on our website. I think the faculty and other departments have a website, at least internally, where they say these are the roles that different people have. I don't think we have that."

c) Initiative and drive despite lack of introduction to the role

Enthusiasm is something that is not easy to capture with a few quotes, but it certainly comes across from the overall feel of the interviews with new staff members. Despite the lack of formal introduction to the role, these newly appointed members show eagerness and a proactive approach.

Having worked in their roles part-time and only for a few months, they didn't waste time. Once they start they go straight into understanding the current status of researchers' awareness and practice of RDM. This response sums up a typical approach to figuring out what the status quo is:

"What I've been doing so far, is on the one hand, I've been going to various meetings related to research data management. I've been studying the role through relevant websites and other universities' web pages. I've been experimenting a bit with different storage systems like Research Drive. And that's all in preparation for my work as a research data coordinator. In addition, I've been having discussions with my colleagues and basically made an inventory of what kind of solutions they're using these days. And what kind of problems they usually run into."

As mentioned above, newly appointed Data Stewards and Data Coordinators do their own research on what's available at the VU. It often leads them to the library resources as well as relying on their own and their colleagues' experience. It seemed that not all of them knew what the best practices actually were.

"I looked at various website pages with regards to RDM at the VU to help myself, to familiarize myself with what's available, what's going on."

"I know that I will find help at the Library, they have a lot of information [on RDM] and I know they have some sort of research data plan course there. Besides that, I do not know yet."

"I know about FAIR principles because I just know that lately, journals ask these questions when you want to publish your work. <...> [Prior to becoming a research data analyst] I had like a couple of courses during my Masters, on the topic of data management, or the practices."

"I also think of my own experience with data management so far. I had this role for 6 months, but I've been working with big data sets for many many years. And clearly, the field has evolved and things have changed. And also the requirements changed."

"Most of it is self taught. I don't have a background in Data Management, primarily because it is not really a way to learn it at a moment. I also do join in a lot of network meetings, not only within the VU, but also external, with more universities. And just a lot of online reading, so there's quite a bit of good resources available online, which I regularly read through."

d) Adaptation and Tailoring to Faculty needs

Data Coordinators and Data Stewards on the ground seemed to realise very quickly how diverse the awareness and practice of RDM on their faculty is. They often point out that the RDM practices differ not just from one faculty to another but also within one faculty.

"Our department is massive. Handling all these many groups, many researchers is really difficult. It's the same for providing guidance for every single group: they have their own way of doing things. So we are really trying to understand what people are doing here in the department right now."

"After our first round of workshops, we realised that people practice RDM very differently. So differently that is even beyond our initial expectation. So we wanted to understand more. And we handed out a questionnaire to our researchers, so they can tell us what they know and what they don't know."

"The University Library provides some kind of guidance, which is good, but, as I said, it is relatively general. But you know, as I mentioned, in our department things are very different."

Although the specific discovery path might be different from one Data Steward to another, running a questionnaire to understand the status quo appeared to be a common practice. The results of the questionnaire often inform the next steps for RDM support for that specific faculty.

"A couple of months ago, I sent a questionnaire to my colleagues within our department asking them okay, what are you using for data solutions? And what are the problems that you're experiencing? So I have those answers. And once the summer is over, I'll talk a bit more about these problems that people are experiencing and see what kind of solutions we can come up with."

When designing their survey, staff members seem to follow their gut feeling and their experience rather than set guidance. In addition, it seems that they place the storage solutions at the heart of what they need to know. In this respect, they are not talking about RDM in a holistic way, as a research data cycle would suggest. This is how one Data Steward explained putting emphasis on questions around storage when running a questionnaire:

"I think storage captures a lot, right? At least part of the collecting of data, analyzing the data, archiving and publishing. At least that's how I see it. So storage is a container that works for a lot of different things. <...> In hindsight, I should have asked in this questionnaire if people are familiar with FAIR practices, and requirements for the publisher data"

3. Community and Network

a) Community meetings play an important role for RDM staff

Various meetings for Data Coordinators and Data Stewards, whether at the faculty or broader levels, play a vital role. They help share insights about RDM roles and best practices, allowing members to learn from each other and improve their RDM approaches.

Lena Karvovskaya was the name that came up consistently when the staff was talking about the meetings and events for the RDM community. (If you are still giving this report your full attention, please know that she prefers drinking her coffee just black, no milk, thank you.) When prompted to think of a network, the respondents immediately talk about the meetings and the sense of community.

“Data Coordinators and Data Stewards meet every two weeks, I think. It’s a lunch meeting and we discuss various things. For me it’s a place to go to ask questions.”

“We have a monthly meeting for our faculty’s Data Stewards. There are at least 10 people constantly attending, and the Head of the faculty also comes, which is good. <...> So, you can come and just listen, but you can also talk about your questions and form relationships.”

“We have this community that is run by Lena, and she is basically the heart of the community. I met a lot of people [who are part of the RDM community] like this. It’s really interesting to see what other people are doing [in their RDM-related roles]. You can listen to what sort of new things are discussed. And then you also know more about what you can do [in your role].”

In fact, the RDM staff often uses the words “community” and “network” interchangeably, not drawing any particular distinction between these concepts. The staff recognises the community as a place where they not only get to listen to what their colleagues are doing but also freely ask for any support they may need.

“We have this network of people across the VU. So, for example, if our group doesn’t know the answers, we send the question to the University RDM team, and they have an email address. And they help us. Or they say who we can talk to.”

“So the university has this entire data management team or network. From the faculty level, from the department level to the university level. And also the IT team is there. And maybe the legal team, I am not sure. So this is a community that is actively being maintained by Lena. So whenever you have a problem or you want to talk to somebody, or you want somebody to talk to somebody, she’s the person to contact. And we all know that there are different meetings that you can come to. So everybody knows what other people are doing.”

b) Noticeable positive impact of NeRDS

With the development of the NeRDS Data Stewards as well as the RDM library team are seeing positive changes:

- Improved knowledge-sharing channels and practices:

“Now we can much better share tools, for example, and also give much more focused and specialised support with very tough problems like levels of sensitivity of data. And the network is helping, because the change in the hierarchy structure also makes it way more possible for these problems to be discussed.”

“Now we have a more central place where we can find all the information regarding data management. Basically, for quite a while you really had to look up some information from one site and then pick something from another site, and now it's starting to be all more central, organised.”

- Stronger collaboration between departments, and more direct support for researchers:

“There were departments we barely spoke with, but now there is a representative from every department, and we can learn about their practices.”

“The fact that we are now installing representatives within every department means that there's a fixed place where people can ask RDM questions. In the past, the general idea was just go to the support desk. And that's too wide, there's a lot of specialism missing there. And then you will get delegated. So there are a lot of steps in between. Now you can go straight to me. That's happening way more frequently now. And also I as a Data Steward know better what's going on in my department”

“What is really nice is that these people who are now supporting RDM in the faculties, are really smart and have great ideas. And we work together.”

- Further fostering a sense of trust and RDM community at VU:

“And it has been really good to set up this not just a community of people, but a community of, say, RDM-consciousness.”

“How the meetings nowadays go are: we're all sitting at a table round table. We can just go discuss stuff that's different than on one side of the table. So it's way more different dynamic. <...> That's happened with the development of the network.”

“If I don't know something, I can ask the group and say, has anyone ever encountered this situation? So that's really nice. And this is really one of Lena's accomplishments since she has really created the platform for this. It's not just organizing meetings, and making sure there are drinks, but it's creating a shared space of trust, where people can really work together.”

c) “I don't work for the network”

Not everyone associates themselves with being part of the network, or believes the NeRDS impacts their job to some extent:

“There's apparently a network of people to share information. And in essence, there's a community, there's a network on sort of that communication interactive level, which like Lena

runs. The network is great and good to be involved in. But as far as formally performing functions, I don't work for the network. Well, that's my opinion. "

"We have this like a grouping of all the people that are involved with data management. Now, it's more of a thing that you can ask the community and then more people might be able to answer questions or help out. But if there was no community, I would probably still evaluate who I can ask, and still probably ask the same person, because I know quite a few people, and I know who knows what."

"I mean, the network itself initially was organised internally as the collaboration between the library and the IT department. I mean, they've organised a lot of stuff internally themselves, which now makes it easier to access knowledge. So the network, in that sense, is a real organising structure. And that's also good, but that doesn't have a really direct effect on me. I still do my job as before."

4. Challenges mentioned by staff

a) Capacity and expectation management

Both new and experienced staff members are anticipating more queries from the researchers as RDM culture is becoming more prominent at the VU. While some are uncertain about expectations, others possess a clearer understanding of how emerging tools and changes could impact their work, prompting potential adjustments.

"At the moment, there are certain extra needs that the Data Stewards do. So, for example, these consultations for the DMPs, the metadata support for Yoda, the infrastructure support, also, looking at the library course thing, where we have to give comments for students. And at the moment I do that for the entire faculty. The idea is that it will be done on the departmental level. But at the moment, it's just not sustainable."

"For now, I only worked on a few inquiries from the people who know me. But as more people will know that I exist in their department, I think questions will rain on me, and I don't know if I will have enough time to answer them."

More experienced staff members desire to successfully convey to the researchers that Data Stewards are not wizards. There is a need to set clear expectations about the time required to understand and assist with researchers' projects. Despite appearing straightforward, tasks like reviewing data management plans entail complexities that demand more time than anticipated, often revealing multiple underlying issues.

"I think some clear expectations about the fact that things take time would be nice to articulate. We are here to help, and we want to help. And in order to help we need to take time to understand their problem and their project."

"I always tell them, people need to expect a week. And yeah, it doesn't take that much time to review a data management plan. But it's not so simple as just reading through the data

management plan and saying, Okay, this is fine, or giving a bit of advice, and it gets fixed. Once we start reading through the data management plan, we start seeing all the problems.”

b) Complex questions and conflicting interests

Experienced faculty staff dealing with intricate research scenarios often face conflicts of interest among departments like the library, IT, and Legal due to the complexity of questions and sensitive data involved.

The staff faces challenges in aligning legal and regulatory requirements with practical research needs. There's also a recurring issue of unclear directives and fragmented communication between specific departments and the central VU, leading to confusion and frustration among researchers and RDM staff.

The stories below illustrate how Data Stewards are trying to do their best, but require more cooperation and support from other teams.

“Sometimes, there are differences of opinion on how to address a privacy concern. Like we've got a discussion going regarding whether or not to inform people that the Qualtrics questionnaire program is an American company. Because it is an American company, we went through a whole process to get a processing agreement in place with Qualtrics. <...> So we've got everything in place. So the idea of informing participants of that and not providing any other further detail will just scare people away. But this is what some of our departments are requesting. And so it leads to a lot of complexity of like, do we just disagree with the legal department even though like they do know more about the legal stuff, but it might create more problems for us on the research side of things? So we kind of end up feeling like a little bit stuck in that regard.”

“With the rollout of the new solution, Yoda, we were told that as soon as it was rolled out, you can use it for high-risk data (and then there was this list item of what it means), but not very high-risk data. But what is very high-risk data? The only examples that they would give us were state secrets and information about the Dutch royal family. But that's never gonna happen in research. What are we supposed to do if we're looking at certain data, and we think “Gee, that's pretty high risk!” What do we do? Do we just say, you can't use Yoda? But then researchers need to use something to store their data.

And so the solution we came up with was, okay, we would tell a researcher [our opinion], and then they get it forwarded to the IT security department just to double check. <...> But it turns out, even making that suggestion, IT has gotten mad at us, because they don't want all these requests!

But you're telling us we can't store very high-risk data there. But then you're not telling us what very high-risk data is, and not coming up with a solution for how we can handle it. <...> And what are we supposed to do with that? Do we just bypass IT and say, Okay, well, I guess, use Yoda and encrypt it? And then if something goes wrong, is it our fault, because we didn't go via IT? We just kind of end up going in circles a lot and not getting the answers.”

“Maybe for the VU or the IT it doesn’t matter if our data is high risk or super high risk, but for us it does. <...> But we don’t have the authority to decide that we need this extra protection of data. This is what makes it difficult. Because we have an idea that yeah, this data must be stored safer, but how exactly to do it is unclear. We don’t have a triple expert in IT, data management, and Legal matters. I don’t think that anyone at the VU is working on it right now.”

“I think we are finding that researchers are kind of getting like bits and pieces of information, some from the library, some information from us [at the faculty]. <...> So sometimes communication that comes out of the library is meant for everyone. <...> And then we have to sort of do damage control and say: “No, you can’t use that, don’t do that.” And that just confuses and frustrates researchers.”

c) RDM support information online is confusing at times.

As has been mentioned, new members of staff are doing their own research to understand what support is available at the VU. To get a full picture, they go to multiple sources of information. For researchers, who may have less devotion to learning about the support available, it could be even more difficult. Even if they find the solutions available, it may still be confusing to understand how to use the solution.

For example, an area to improve is the information about “How to write a DMP”:

“It is so important and I think that it should be just easy to sign up [for the course]. But I see that there are no future dates, for example. I don’t know. So if I say to a researcher that there is this course, then I don’t know how they will sign up for this.”

Yet another example covers the whole spectrum of RDM-related webpages:

“So when I was googling what we have, sometimes I would see different information in different places or at random places. Sometimes it is outdated. But then I discover that there are other pages with some good guidance that I didn’t know about.”

Some users also required additional support using the storage finder:

“It’s great that we have this storage finder website. But one thing that is missing to me is the practical connection, like how to access a storage system that I choose? Because it varies. And then I want to know whether I can use it for long term, if I can use it in collaboration with others, and that kind of stuff. <...> Providing that important practical information like storage limits, accessibility and other stuff is there, it would be easy to choose.”

“It has got several storage options listed, that we all agree aren’t really appropriate for research data. And so I don’t know why it’s on the storage finder. But it just leads to more confusion.”

d) Unsure where the boundaries of the role are

Some new and experienced Data Stewards mention that with the development of the NeRDS, they are not sure where their responsibilities end and NeRDS support begins. It is expressed in several examples, some of which are below and some are illustrated in the next section:

“I think sometimes the projects are so complex, like with that example where we needed a new software, that it’s just not feasible for any of the Data Stewards who are involved, to take on being project managers. We don’t have the time and we don’t have the skillset. I think the NeRDS has a responsibility to it in terms of being a group that coordinates the RDM support, data stewards, IT, and legal. But sometimes it gets confusing because NeRDS is all of us. But we are not contract managers.”

“So maybe because I haven’t been doing it for too long, sometimes I don’t know if I am supposed to know it or if it’s something that requires input from other people”

5. Good to have for staff

Before diving into this chapter, be aware that you are almost half way through the report and if you have been reading this carefully, you now totally deserve some Grolsch or Hertog-Jan!

a) Proper introduction to the role and further training

As has been shown above, new members of staff, although being full of enthusiasm and eager to deliver results haven’t had a proper introduction to the role.

They may not talk about it explicitly, but they are often unsure of the scope of their responsibilities, the amount of workload they might be having in the future, and, more importantly, of the full collection of tools and services available at the VU.

They certainly find a lot of support through chatting with their peers at various meetings, but a lack of formal onboarding may create gaps of knowledge about RDM for those who must know all about it.

“Some sort of onboarding would be useful. Right? Especially when it comes to, let’s say, making clear what the remit is for the position.”

“I just wanted to understand how these storage solutions differ, so I can explain it better to the researchers because there is not much information on them in this storage finder. So I just played with some of them a bit myself.”

b) Feedback on suggestions and DMPs

Due to the nature of the RDM service being re-active, RDM support staff doesn’t receive regular feedback on their work from researchers. There is no visible system of collecting and analysing feedback from researchers on what worked and what didn’t.

Data Stewards and Data Coordinators occasionally know if the solution worked and all went well, but it is mainly done through random feedback from researchers. Despite each project being unique to some extent, it results in RDM support staff, including IT, having less confidence in giving similar advice for similar types of research projects, which could have speeded up the process of support.

“The thing is, we don’t really know if our solutions work. If they don’t work, people might get back to us and ask again for help. But not always, I think. Or maybe they can go somewhere else and search for another solution. And if our solution worked, we also don’t know how well it worked. We just don’t get this type of feedback.”

“I think sometimes we keep re-inventing the wheel. We know there was a similar project, but we don’t know if that solution worked for it. And maybe this time we do the work from scratch again instead of just saying: “It worked for this, so you probably will be fine too if you do the same”.”

“I have commented on so many DMPs. I don’t know how many of them actually worked in practice according to the plan.”

However, some highlight that having such a feedback system will potentially add more work:

“Of course, more information is better. But there are only 24 hours in a day, and with the small team that we have to support researchers, I just don’t know how [the feedback system] can be done. It kind of works as it is now. But if we want to make it better, this needs to be done with the whole research community together.”

c) Awareness of emerging complex projects

Ideally, RDM support staff prefer early notification of upcoming complex research projects to adequately assist researchers in finding optimal RDM solutions. Some academics who have experience working with RDM staff, have a habit of informing the Library or Data Stewards about the projects as early as possible, as they realise the value of this. However, this is not always the case.

“We try as many ways as possible, send out repeated reminders. We have an easily findable website, constant newsletters, all these things, but researchers are busy and they’re focused on “I just need to get my grant in place. Oh, oh, no, I’m starting research tomorrow. Oh, no, this isn’t working.” And if there was a way that we had a sense of what research-specific projects were starting, especially complex ones, we might be able to like, flag something in advance and talk to the technical support department. We need to talk to the researcher about it before they’re already at the point of the ethics committee.”

d) More visible support from the NeRDS

The staff members expressed a desire for NeRDS to enhance support for major projects, akin to the presence of project managers in other faculties. In addition, the staff expressed the need for NeRDS to take ownership of crucial issues, particularly regarding data sensitivity, where some Data Stewards feel somewhat isolated.

"I think such complex projects [like getting a new transcription software] should be more supported by the NeRDS. Sometimes I feel like it's just my responsibility, but I am a Data Steward and not a Project Manager. I know one faculty started having Project managers, specifically for research, someone whose job it is to oversee large projects. Maybe NeRDS should do it as well for some of the projects that are happening within NeRDS."

"What I would like to see from NeRDS is a bit of like taking ownership of complex issues. I feel like with these data sensitivity levels we kind of been left alone. But this is an important issue."

There's also a request for greater participation and engagement from NeRDS and central VU figures in meetings to facilitate better communication and sharing of the latest developments.

"A little bit more participating in meetings from the central level. So for example, these lunch meetings I was talking about will be good. It will be very interesting if one of the NeRDS people or one of the central VU people comes and introduces themselves and tells us something about the latest developments. At the moment it's been delegated or not been done."

When it comes to organising information on RDM-related matters across various websites, NeRDS is also perceived as an entity that should be more coordinated and united, making sure the information is consistent and up to date.

"I know that NeRDS is like all of us, but there should be more agreement and, maybe, more awareness of what information needs to be updated. Some library webpages still have stuff that we don't really use anymore, and when new tools are rolled out, we should all update it, so the researchers are not confused."

PART 2. RESEARCHERS' PERSPECTIVE

1. How do researchers think about data management?

a) What is data management for researchers?

In 2020 it was clear that there is no holistic understanding of what research data management is. Commonly people thought about it as a number of things they need to do and the rules they need to follow. It doesn't seem dramatically different today. But there is more talk about how RDM is connected to the integrity and impact of the research. People also mention Open Science Framework as part of RDM field. In this sense, those who know about RDM, think about RDM more holistically. However, it is still difficult for them to describe what they mean by good research data management.

"I work as a guest researcher, and I don't need to take any courses. Because I come from a Research Masters programme, I know a little bit about this."

"Through my academic career, I learned how to organize my data, like making a proper folder system to find what I want when I need it. That, I think, is the major thing."

"[When I think of what research data management means,] I don't really know. I think it's like how I work with my dataset during research."

"Well, I know that I need a good structure to organise [my data] and take care of it because it matters for integrity and the quality of research. But you don't know what you will have, in a way. So how can you plan? Every once in a while I sit and I try to organise my data a bit. But it's not like I plan it and think ahead."

Experienced researchers and associate professors see the bigger picture and try to help their peers and students do the same. They also appreciate the changes and recognise there is more support available and more tools are introduced.

"I [work on DMPs] together with my students. I take a lot of time to teach my PhD candidates how to do RDM correctly and why it's important. <...> It's much easier to do now because there is a lot more available."

"Over the past few years, there have been a lot of improvements in conducting research according to the guidelines. The Open Science Framework, the PURE thing, the Research Portal. It all is getting more integrated, much easier to integrate. And also there is more availability of datasets and syntaxes for our projects."

"It feels that people are taking it more seriously these days. There is a lot of support available. Now there are more Data Stewards and the Library now has more solutions."

b) How do researchers learn about data management practices?

Compared to 2020, there is a greater diversity of sources of learning. Often they mix and match those sources of information. Some young researchers have an idea about what RDM is **even before they start their PhD**. Some courses are now available to Masters students on work ethics and data management that provide an initial introduction to the field.

“I was aware of these processes before my PhD. I had courses on work ethics and such, and there was never a situation where I was in conflict or had some misunderstanding. I just always did it to the best of my knowledge. And so this course [on DMP] just confirmed most of my beliefs that I had before.”

Others learn about RDM through **emails**, newsletters, and VU events.

“When I met [RDM support staff member] at the FAIR data event, I was very surprised to learn that we have a Data Steward in our department. Because I didn’t know that such a person existed”

Yet others mention that they go to the internal PhD **meetings** where other PhD students can present their work. During those meetings, in some cases, there are discussions about the difficulty of getting through the ethics committee, which serves as an opportunity to ask questions about data management.

“So those presentations are quite transparent. And sometimes you hear people have trouble getting through ethics approvals, and then you can ask them why that is and how they approach it. Sometimes they have huge datasets and they struggle with processing. So then you ask them how they store their data, and what they do with it. And you learn kind of passively a bit about practices from others.”

Going to **colleagues or a supervisor** remains the most popular option nevertheless. Especially for those PhD students who are not obliged to take the DMP course.

“When it comes to additional stuff like that my first instinct is just always to go to my supervisor!”

“My supervisor cared that I had the checks done for my survey. But they didn’t ask me for a data management plan. And it’s not like they are going to ask me if I store my files correctly.”

“I know that other PhD student, who is further along, so I talk to them. And they can help you out. And you can learn from other people like that.”

Some particularly enthusiastic PhD students go on a **self-discovery quest** and this way they quickly grasp the whole spectrum of all things related to RDM at the VU and beyond.

“I’m just really interested in Open Science. And I have a couple of colleagues who did a course on research data management, so I looked it up, and I also signed up. And after that, I discovered many other courses and events like this. It’s all self-discovery for me.”

“I took a refinery workshop, a literature finding course, a data management plan course, and I

also started to be on mailing lists about events on reproducible research and workshops on coding”

c) Writing DMP remains a vital introductory tool for researchers

Similar to 2020, those who write a DMP have a much more solid understanding of data management. Those who take the course find it a very valuable experience. It also often serves as an opportunity for the RDM professionals to introduce themselves to the researchers on their faculty.

“The guy who led the course actually gave some recommendations and recommended ways to better our RDM solutions. Like, if you are coming from that angle, this is a recommended way, if you come with this kind of data, look at this. And that was really applicable and very actionable.”

However, for those starting late or not obliged to the Plan, DMPs seem like wasted time.

“I don’t think we did anything with [our DMP]. We didn’t need to submit it somewhere or something. I think it still exists somewhere. But no one ever asked. <...> I think it helps you guide how you think about your data. But I think it was too detailed for us and too late. We wouldn’t change what we do because of it.”

“There are a lot of people who think you should do things. I think it should really come from the supervisor directly. <...> When I was told about the DMP [which was not compulsory for my project], I was a bit scared that it would not be worth my time to actually do it.”

When researchers write a DMP, they think of the whole RDM cycle and try to answer questions comprehensively. But they also suspect that in reality, those answers might not apply, or may need to change. They doubt they can adhere to the plan fully, which feels off-putting.

“[In my DMP] I wrote okay, you have to do it like this and like this. But then the moment you sit down and you do it, like actually have the discipline to follow the same structure, it’s pretty difficult to organise. Because you learn as you go, you kind of try and okay, this doesn’t work. So it becomes messy anyway. I don’t think you can follow your plan as you wrote it.”

Yet, some realise greater potential in the DMP, even though they haven’t written it. DMP for them is a document that helps to communicate the RDM practices from one researcher to another. Such realisation is something that didn’t exist in 2020.

“Now that I think about [how I organise my folders], it may not be so obvious for other people, for someone external. I guess that’s something the data management plan would help with. Like, how do I communicate the system that I’ve used for myself to make it also useful for others?”

On the other end of the spectrum, those who have finished their PhD without knowing of a DMP or RDM-related practices, have no idea why one may need the data management plan. They continue working in the same way.

"I know that the new PhDs have this research data management plan. But I'm not particularly aware of what exactly the plan is. I don't know what it means."

2. How do researchers find support for their data management practices?

a) More information on VU websites

In contrast with 2020, where researchers didn't make good use of the information available online, this time it is often mentioned that websites are useful. They provide good basic support to understand not just what RDM is and how to think about it, but also illustrate the tools available for support. However, people tend not to remember the exact website and they tend to find it via Google instead of going directly there. Some of them need time to find it again, but as they type the keywords, they are often quickly able to find what they need.

"Research support portal website is quite handy. It has improved over time. [Now] there is a lot of information on the website and you don't necessarily need to have a meeting with an expert."

"I don't remember what [the website] is called. I usually google it through the VU and it pops up. Last time I needed something about how to use Qualtrics, and I found it there."

"I go to your department's website, you know, the library one, about RDM"

b) Researchers know RDM support is available at their faculties

Compared to 2020, where it has been discovered that researchers often learn about RDM support by accident or by word of mouth, there's a noticeable shift in 2023: most interviewed researchers are aware of departmental RDM support. However, not all engage with Data Stewards or Coordinators.

"I learned in the [Writing a DMP] course that each department has a Data Steward. So I know mine. And I know that the assignment for that course needs to be approved by him. <...> I read his name on the assignment, but I haven't seen him in person."

"When we had to do the ethics check for our survey, and my Data Steward helped. <...> To be honest, I don't remember how I knew her. I just knew that we had a Data Steward. But maybe it was my colleague who told me about her."

But they don't tend to go to the RDM support with any questions. PhD students commonly think that simple questions are something they should solve themselves. Yet, they would go to the Data Steward if faced with more complex questions.

"I go to your RDM department in the library with complex issues. These little daily struggles I try to figure out myself"

"I don't see your [RDM support department at the library] like the IT Help Desk, where you can just go, walk by and ask questions. I see it as helpful for larger things."

“For very specific questions I would probably go to [the Data Coordinator], she is in the office next door, so it’s very very easy.”

However, sometimes those who are not very well aware of RDM practices, are surprised by the suggestions that Data Stewards are giving them.

“When we came to discuss our project [with the Data Steward], she said we also need to write a data management plan. And we need to think about other things. I think it’s very strange that she told us that we have to write it. My supervisor didn’t tell me that. And I was thinking, do I really need to do all of this?”

Some are aware that the Library also provides support with many aspects of research data management, and once they ask somebody an RDM-related question, they prefer approaching this person again, instead of finding someone new.

“I will just go straight to the library. That’s where the main expertise is in providing accessibility to the information and making the publication openly available.”

“I just knew her already. She helped me before, so that’s why [I came to her again]. I know I could have gone to my Data Steward, but I haven’t met the guy, I don’t even know how to contact him.”

c) Experience and teamwork help

Experienced research staff mention that the basic questions remain the same over time. Often, these questions come up again and again. They are not surprised or annoyed by this situation, rather, they draw solutions from experience. Experience makes the RDM seem like part of the process of research rather than a burden.

“It’s not a lot of work, but it needs some careful thinking. We do a lot of research that doesn’t need to be checked formally through the ethics committee. It’s just self-check and then okay, good luck. But when things get a bit more different than the most general setup, people start thinking: Oh what do I do now? And most of them by now know how to find RDM support in the library or find another colleague who can help.”

“I am lucky that I have so much experience working with datasets. So from trial and error, I know what works, and how to better organise the data.”

“I’ve been working with datasets many years now, and so I know where the problems are going to be.”

More experienced staff also mention that teamwork helps. Whenever they have a quick question or something they are unsure of, they now engage in collaborative discussions with colleagues for quick RDM queries, a shift from 2020 when such conversations were absent for basic RDM questions. This collaborative approach has emerged as a significant change over time.

“These little questions just need mostly some sparring with a colleague to solve.”

“I think there is a lot more teamwork lately. So recently there has been a lot more focus on doing things together. It’s very hands-on, we do many things together. So I think it’s gotten better. But a lot of researchers are still not in the office, and they work in their own little groups.”

Younger researchers, who may not have their DMPs written, just follow their colleagues and the rest of the group.

“So I also learn from other researchers. Because we talk about it, you know. I look at how they organise their workflow, and if it makes sense to me, I just apply it to my projects as well.”

3. Obstacles researchers face using RDM services

a) Researchers ask for help only when they realise they might have an issue

Similar to the situation in 2020, it seems that researchers still care about solving RDM-related questions when the time comes. If it is not urgent, they don’t tend to worry. It is visible across all spectrums of experience: from those who are doing their PhD to the experienced assistant professors.

“[Talking about the storage solutions for raw data:] We are currently not sure what the best way for this is. [But] it’s not urgent, we are not at that phase yet. The last time we spoke [with RDM support] was a while back. And there were already some developments within the RDM department, so we are kind of waiting. When those new software packages come up, we can see okay, is this what we need?”

“This is my last year, and I have a very hard deadline. <...> I know we’ve been thinking of how we will archive the data. And we also think about what we need for publication. But right now I have other priorities, I can’t deal with it.”

b) It requires extra time to change practices

Similar to 2020, time is of paramount importance for researchers. Once they start following a workflow or use a particular solution, it is very difficult for them to change the practices later on. Even if they know that what they are doing is not ideal.

While in 2020 researchers talked about new rules and new tools they had to learn and adopt, this time the focus was much more on storage solutions.

Those who don’t work with sensitive data and are far along with their PhD are happy to continue using less-than-ideal storage solutions.

“So I think many of us are paranoid about keeping our data safe. So we have a backup on the hard disk, which I think is more conventional. Just in case. But many of us use Dropbox or Google Drive or something like that to store that data. Because my data is usually not so

confidential, we don't study humans. So we usually don't care that much about confidentiality or anything like that. <...> I know University has different data storage systems."

However, those who do want to find a better storage solution and are willing to spend time, think carefully before choosing one. And understandably get frustrated when they need to relocate their data.

"We came to [our Data Steward] with a storage question. And it was very confusing. We had a lot of IT problems, to be honest. So we started two sets. We only use one now. I used the Surf Drive, and then it crashed. And then [the Data Steward] told me to move to OneDrive, so I moved to OneDrive. And then she told me to use Research Drive. And it's very confusing and frustrating. You have all these different ways of storing files, but which one has the functionality that you need for your specific project?"

The problem of changing practices in general, however, seems smaller, possibly due to the early introduction to the right tools and RDM policies, so the researchers are better prepared in general.

c) Enrolling in RDM courses is challenging and they may not fully cater to one's needs

Accessing and finishing mandatory courses is tough due to unclear schedules and communication, eating into valuable research time. While some mandatory courses cover crucial topics like scientific integrity, their effectiveness in engaging participants is questioned at times.

"Finding the course and finding when and where to apply for it is incredibly hard. Finding a slot is incredibly hard because usually the courses are once a year and it doesn't say when new times will be communicated. Usually, there is a contact of the person who does the course, but if you reach out to them and ask when the next course will be, they say they don't know."

"So, for the integrity course, they have limited spots, and because you can't have a class with 50 students, they have to wait until there is a spot available, which sometimes takes time. <...>"

"The challenge for me is that I don't have a lot of time for my PhD. And this course is compulsory. So you just try to do it. And then you spend so much time figuring out how to sign up. This is not something I should spend my time on, I think."

"Scientific integrity [course] was mandatory. And when I learned about it, I immediately started to actively try to sign up and do it. But it still took me almost a year to finish it. <...> It was very boring. I am not sure I learned a lot from these discussions."

Researchers noted that in addition to being introduced to the best practices during the DMP course, they also desire more practical examples, especially on what to avoid and why.

"Everybody tells you what you should do. But for this course, it would also be nice to see what you shouldn't do. And it can be an easy checklist to see whether they do any of these practices. And if I see okay this is something I am not supposed to do, then I know I have to change it."

d) Choosing the storage is confusing and at times frustrating

The introduction of the storage finder solution has been mentioned by researchers on several occasions. Although they are happy that this tool exists, they noticed that the solution was not ideal. There is not enough information to choose the right one for them.

"It took me a while to figure out the best storage solution. I kind of spend a lot of time thinking about it and researching it. <...> Yes, I used the storage finder thing, it's good that we have it, but it was confusing. I still had to choose. And I wasn't sure I was choosing the right thing"

"Yeah, I know we had a storage finder, but I preferred to talk to my Data Steward about it."

e) Unsure who to contact about data management systems

Several researchers pointed out that when they had problems with data management systems, they had no idea who to contact and how long it may take for someone to help them. It is especially worrying when problems with accessing storage occur.

"You just contact everyone you know, basically. <...> The RDM department didn't help. You get no response or get something after two or three weeks, but the problems you have, you have to solve within now and three, or four hours. You cannot wait for two or three weeks. <...> But sometimes you wait so long that the problem solves itself, somehow. But you are so stressed during this time."

"There was an error with my Qualtrics account, and I couldn't access it. I really struggled because I didn't know. And it was really hard for me to find who to contact, and I went through several circles. And apparently, there is one person in the whole VU who can unblock the accounts!"

4. What do researchers wish to receive from RDM support?

a) Start early

The vast majority of researchers wished they had been introduced to RDM practices early. Those who are halfway through their PhD and had completed the RDM course, in the beginning, highlight how it has helped them to make sense of research data management and prepared or even inspired them to think about the Open Science framework.

"Yes, of course in practice I didn't follow everything in my DMP. But honestly, it just made my life a lot easier just knowing that I need to think about it."

Associate professors shared the feelings of some of their researchers who discovered DMP or Research Integrity courses at the very end of their PhD:

"When they are writing up their thesis and they learn about the course, they are all so surprised: "Oh, this is how you are supposed to store your data! This is how I have to deal with my

supervisor when I disagree! Oh, I shouldn't have put this person as a co-author on my paper!" and so on. And yes, it's so important to see good examples at the start, and it can make your life a lot easier. I always encourage everyone in my department to take these courses as soon as possible. "

The point applies equally to those who have written their DMP too late and those who haven't done it all.

"I found out about it a year after I started my PhD, and I think it's way too late to find out that you need to write a data management plan."

"I think someone just mentioned somewhere, that there is this course, and it's useful. It's not compulsory for me, but I wish I had to do it and also at the very beginning of the PhD, not after I randomly discovered it. And now I am just telling everyone like yeah, you have to do it, and you have to contact this person because otherwise they don't know."

b) Involve supervisors

Similarly to the situation in 2020, the supervisor remains one of the most important people in the life of a researcher.

In 2020 researchers told us that a supervisor may or may not introduce a researcher to the RDM, emphasise its importance, help them find support, be interested in helping the researcher follow FAIR principles and/or publish their paper through the OSF.

This time researchers specifically wish to see support or at least acknowledgement of the importance of following RDM practices from their supervisors or PIs.

"It feels like [RDM support staff] works really hard to make this issue important. I think they need to get the urgency across. But I also think it should come from the supervisors as well. I think if the Why? comes across better, people will be more motivated to also do it."

"Unfortunately, I think the issue is that professors or PIs are not aware that this skill needs to be taught. So that's why they don't see the point of having such a course."

"My supervisor knew the Privacy Officer from the previous projects, so she introduced us and we sat together and talked through our project, and she could think along with us, what we needed regarding privacy and data management things and from that, she directed us to the right department. <...> I think because I saw that it's important for my supervisor, I also took it very seriously."

c) Don't miss out on exciting stuff!

RDM community provides fantastic all-rounded support for researchers on all sorts of issues. There are events, meetings, courses. However, some topics are overlooked. Despite significant developments emerging within the last few months around AI, the lack of proactive communication from RDM support staff about these technological advancements is apparent. This gap indicates a

potential disconnect between researchers and the support available to help them navigate and leverage these new advancements effectively.

"I think over the last six-eight months there were many things that appeared out of thin air, from text generation to image generation, to programming assistance. And yes, I guess it was the time for the research support to shine, to talk to researchers, and help them navigate the space. There aren't many moments in history like this when dramatic changes are happening. But they completely missed out on it. I haven't heard any communication about AI and how it impacts research."

EMERGING FINDINGS:

Persisting challenges

Compared to 2020, some things have stayed the same.

Those who are not aware of RDM courses and practices face the same issues and challenges. Three years ago, they hesitated to ask questions about RDM, thinking that it was their responsibility to figure out the solution. They may use Dropbox or Google Drive if the data is not sensitive (however, they are all aware of how sensitive their data is. There wasn't one researcher interviewed who worked with sensitive data and used storage not recommended by the VU!).

They may know that there is a Data Steward in their department but never think of a reason to contact them. For these researchers, the user journey designed in 2020 stays the same.

Another aspect that hasn't changed since 2020 is the role of a supervisor or PI.

If a supervisor talks about aspects of RDM, including appropriate storage, FAIR principles, archiving, and even file management or introduces them to a Data Steward/ Privacy Champion at the faculty, researchers are much more likely to take the issue seriously. If the supervisor doesn't pay attention to RDM, researchers don't perceive it as something important either.

More familiarity, less hesitation

In contrast to the situation in 2020, the landscape of RDM appears to have evolved beyond a mere focus on regulations and DMPs. Researchers now engage in a diverse array of events and courses encompassing RDM, Open Science, and FAIR principles. They navigate through various tools like Qualtrics, Yoda, and GitHub.

Participation in VU-wide and Faculty-specific meetings exposes them to multifaceted RDM-related subjects. As they immerse themselves in these activities, they encounter VU staff and an expanded spectrum of RDM themes. This exposure sometimes leads to new discoveries, and occasionally leaves researchers uncertain and confused.

Nonetheless, most importantly there is less hesitation in approaching these subjects. These questions range from quick and simple to more complex and at times very urgent, that researchers email or ask face-to-face. Of course, not all questions are asked, and researchers still firmly believe that RDM is their responsibility. However, the variety of questions is much richer compared to the study in 2020.

DMP is more than a tick-box exercise

The DMP stands as a vital entry point into comprehending the entirety of the research data journey, enabling researchers to anticipate numerous challenges in advance. Beyond its fundamental role, some perceive the DMP as having greater potential. This notion is completely new and did not show up in 2020's research at all.

Some researchers regard the DMP not just as a requisite document but also as a collaborative tool fostering cohesion within teams, and facilitating collective understanding, whether they commence as a cohesive group or integrate new members into ongoing projects.

The fact that there are researchers who still have little idea of the importance of RDM and don't know what DMP is for further emphasises the need for an earlier introduction and potentially mandatory inclusion of this tool for all researchers.

Ideal versus reality

Often researchers believe that writing a DMP and following it to the letter or following the best practices of RDM is an ideal that can never be reached. For some such realisation is disheartening, leads to a decrease in motivation to follow good RDM and might even be perceived as a wasted time.

It might be helpful to think about how RDM support staff can better manage the expectations of researchers. For example, supporting researchers in realising that the DMP could be a living document that evolves with the project and serves as a guide rather than a set-in-stone principle would decrease anxiety around this issue. Of course, it may not be possible at times when a fully written DMP is required by an external actor.

On the other hand, while the RDM support is getting stronger, it is worth remembering that despite efforts, not all researcher queries might have immediate solutions, and not every problem may be resolved. It is important to recognize that despite offering advice, there's no guarantee all researchers will follow it. RDM support team is still finding its balance in embracing continuous improvement while being mindful of the practical constraints inherent in managing research data.

(As we pivot to the final chapter, and after being with you, the reader, for the whole 32 pages, the author of this report – Anna Dubov – humbly wants to add a personal note on *ideal versus reality*. The dream of the author is a simple yet distant delight: a herring stall, just a stone's throw from her doorstep, offering the briny bounty of fresh raw herring. But being tucked away in the bustling heart of London, I think this is a luxury seemingly reserved for the denizens of Amsterdam. Ah... maybe one day I'll enjoy a proper herring hot dog in Amsterdam instead of having fish and chips in London!)

RECOMMENDATIONS AND NEXT STEPS

The RDM support is much stronger established at the VU compared to the situation in 2020. One of the underlying goals of the 2020 research was to understand how to increase awareness of RDM services for researchers. In 2023 the RDM support is established much stronger. The level of awareness is higher, a number of RDM solutions is larger, and the availability of support is more extensive, allowing researchers to navigate complex data management challenges with greater confidence and efficiency.

While recommendations from the 2020 report are still useful for ensuring the awareness level stays high, the focus of recommendations this time is shifted from simply raising awareness to developing deeper strategies that drive behaviour change through meaningful action.

Making the public more aware of an issue can, of course, be a critical step in creating an environment where change is possible. However, once a certain level of awareness is achieved, the next step is to move beyond the awareness towards building new habits and changing the behaviour.

1. Advocate for starting early!

Based on the interviews and the information available on the VU website, the RDM community has done a lot of work on promoting RDM awareness. There are now various educational and awareness initiatives available for researchers at different levels, strong collaboration with various support services, and initiatives that stimulate ongoing support for researchers.

It is evident, that started introducing the RDM practice early makes a big difference. Consider doing the following:

- advocate for more departments to adopt “How to write a DMP” as a compulsory course for their researchers,
- collaborate with administrative departments to include RDM components in the orientation or onboarding process for new researchers. This ensures that RDM is introduced from the outset of their academic journey,
- work closely with faculty members and supervisors to emphasise the significance of RDM. Encourage them to incorporate RDM discussions into their courses and mentorship sessions,
- make sure all your online resources are easily accessible, such as online guides, videos, or FAQs, and are specifically designed for beginners.

2. Design onboarding for new RDM staff

The VU dramatically increased the number of RDM support staff over the last 3-4 years. However, internally the VU was not prepared for such an increase. New Data Stewards and Data Coordinators lack proper introduction to RDM support available at the VU as well as to their roles. It is especially worrying that the new staff members:

- don't seem to confidently be able to talk about the pros and cons of various solutions,
- have no instructions on how to approach researchers,
- overlook some elements of the research lifecycle when designing their questionnaire,
- and have little awareness of how their departments practice RDM.

This could lead to inconsistent advice given to researchers.

Designing a proper onboarding is crucial. And it is not too late to start now. The onboarding experience should cover the gaps identified above as well as other steps. There are a few things the VU must consider when designing such an onboarding process.

Avoid unsupported immersion. The way it currently works is a new staff member is left to investigate what's available on their own. Such unsupported immersion can be overwhelming and restrictive (i.e. a new staff member may do deep research into certain parts of RDM support and overlook other parts that are more complex or less interesting for them).

Avoid front-loaded instruction. On the other hand, making the new staff go through training or a pile of information that covers everything they ever need to know right after they have been appointed to the RDM role, also leads to challenges later on. It is hard to remember, can make RDM service seem overly complicated, and it is focused on awareness instead of follow-through. Simply raising the awareness of what exists does not guarantee the action we want them to take.

When designing your onboarding, create an experience of a **guided interaction**. Be deliberate in guiding your new RDM members every step of the way. Make sure you do the following:

- Connect the information to the meaningful actions that the onboarding experience enables, instead of explaining things out of context.
- Decouple the important actions of your onboarding experience, so new users in different situations can encounter them at the time and in the order that suits them, using guidance to lead to the next steps that build toward a long-term goal.
- Embrace a "new user mindset". Talk to new users to understand what they expect and why, what they know and don't know about the RDM support and solutions available, as well as how their roles fit in the process. Talk to experienced staff members to check what works for them. Spend time exploring questions and getting answers to the points below. This will help you find gaps in your existing onboarding:
 - How and why did they find/choose RDM support for/ as part of their role at the VU?
 - How have they approached trying to find other types of support at the VU or RDM support at other places?
 - What common routines do experienced staff lean on?
 - What workarounds have experienced staff developed?

- Ask new staff members to journal their onboarding experiences
- Explore RDM support (including communication within the RDM community and between RDM staff and researchers) in a “new user mode”, roleplaying within the team.

It’s normal for the proper onboarding to be 3-6 months long, sometimes longer, introducing the service and the job requirements step by step at the right time.

Work with an experienced UX/service designer to design an onboarding that fully meets the needs of the RDM support staff and ensures high engagement and low rotation rate, which in return results in more professional support.

3. Strengthen communication with researchers

The RDM department stands as a vital support system for university researchers, yet the system of communication between RDM staff and researchers seems to lack crucial elements. Communication gaps below have been identified through the interviews with Researchers and RDM support staff.

- Introductory guidance
- The role of the supervisor
- The feedback mechanism

Introductory guidance: There is an absence of clear guidelines for new RDM staff to engage with researchers. This presents a significant hurdle. They approach researchers as they see logical, which may not necessarily be effective or even enough.

An introduction of guidelines outlining when, how, and with what message new members should approach researchers is imperative. The guidelines don’t have to just be on paper. The VU has developed a remarkable variety of meetings between RDM support staff. Use those to share good and bad introductions to RDM stories dated a few years back and discuss them.

Such a more structured approach not only assists new staff in familiarising themselves with the researcher community but also ensures consistency and clarity in conveying the services offered.

The role of the supervisor: The crucial role of supervisors in researchers' projects has been underscored repeatedly. However, this particular aspect remains underdeveloped, despite the 2020 recommendation emphasising the need for closer collaboration. Researchers are more inclined to adopt robust RDM practices when they see explicit support from their supervisors.

Work closely with faculty members and supervisors to emphasise the significance of RDM. Encourage them to incorporate RDM discussions into their courses and mentorship sessions.

Establishing direct relationships with supervisors should be a priority, fostering an environment where RDM becomes an integrated component of research projects.

The feedback mechanism: Although compared to 2020, there is strong progress towards creating a space for knowledge sharing between RDM staff, the current feedback mechanism employed by RDM support staff lacks continuity and comprehensiveness. Relying on sporadic and anecdotal feedback from returning researchers limits the department's understanding of their impact.

Consider introducing a more deliberate and diverse approach that goes beyond routine meetings of RDM support staff. This may include:

- actively seeking updates on solutions proposed,
- checking in 6-12 months whether the DMP a Data Steward commented on has changed or not,
- implementing feedback plugins within newsletters or emails disseminated by the RDM staff.
- always start with the user. Ask the researchers to give suggestions on what is the best way for *them* to give you feedback.

Consider running a team brainstorming session with an experienced facilitator in order to come up with other ideas as a combination of them could serve as a convenient avenue to gather diverse perspectives and insights.

4. Work together accepting the differences

There is a need to clearly define the division of responsibilities between faculties and the wider VU when supporting researchers with their RDM activities.

Throughout the interviews, the point of the VU RDM policies and practices vs faculty-specific policies and practices has been raised several times. Both researchers and staff members get confused when in complex situations or with new solutions being introduced they come across conflicts of interest between the wider VU and a specific faculty.

Consider adopting the initiatives outlined below. If any of these are already in place, consider re-evaluating their efficiency.

Develop clear guidelines. Create comprehensive guidelines that outline the roles, responsibilities, and decision-making frameworks for both the wider VU and individual faculties regarding RDM. These guidelines should address common scenarios, conflicts, and the process for resolving them. Consider co-designing such guidance through cross-departmental workshops instead of adopting a top-down approach. Communicate them clearly. Use the North Star workshop results as a starting point.

Establish designated points of contact. Appoint dedicated individuals or teams within each faculty and the wider VU responsible for RDM coordination. These points of contact can serve as resources for clarification, guidance, and conflict resolution.

Create cross-functional committees. Form cross-functional committees involving representatives from faculties and the wider VU to address complex RDM issues. These committees can assess conflicts, evaluate solutions, and propose aligned strategies.

Establish feedback mechanisms. Establish feedback mechanisms to gather input from researchers and staff members. This feedback can highlight areas of confusion or conflict, guiding continuous improvement efforts. Use metrics co-designed during the North Star workshop as your starting point and work from there.

Recognise faculty specificity. Acknowledge and embrace the uniqueness of each faculty's research landscape, data types, and requirements. Communicate clearly to the staff and researchers alike that while certain practices are recommended for the entire VU, faculties might require nuanced approaches or additional support due to their distinct contexts.

Encourage customised support from Data Stewards. Empower Data Stewards within faculties to provide tailored guidance, training, or adaptations of recommended practices based on the specific needs and intricacies of their researchers' work. Make sure researchers understand and appreciate the level of authority of their Data Steward.

Recognise your limitations. Acknowledge that not all the questions may have an answer, and there is currently a limit to the RDM support at the VU. Not all the researchers will follow RDM best practices, even when working closely with RDM support staff. Not all the demands from researchers could be solved, even with the most hard-working and coordinated people in the community. Make peace with this situation and work towards minimising, not eliminating this.

5. Re-frame the DMP purpose

It has been proven that early taking a DMP course is highly beneficial for researchers in helping them holistically understand the aspects of the RDM. However, researchers mostly think about writing the DMP as a useful yet still box-ticking exercise. Redefining the purpose and approach towards Data Management Plans may transform them from mere obligatory paperwork into valuable, actionable tools for researchers.

RDM support at VU already works towards this, offering personalised support that caters to researchers' specific disciplines and project needs.

Working with the RDM community, consider incorporating the following initiatives into RDM support:

- Promote collaboration and team alignment through DMP for group projects
- Encourage flexibility and adaptability
- Integrate updating a DMP into the research workflow
- Highlight value beyond funding

Promote collaboration and team alignment through DMP for group projects. Emphasize the role of DMPs in aligning diverse research teams. Encourage collaborative DMP development to foster a shared understanding of data management practices and responsibilities among team members. Consider Data Stewards creating a slightly different approach to helping on DMP for group projects, emphasising the role of a DMP as an alignment and accountability tool.

Encourage flexibility and adaptability. Stress the importance of a living DMP that evolves alongside the research. Researchers should feel empowered to update and refine the plan as the project progresses and as data needs change. Consider creating an internal workflow where a Data Steward would check on researchers, whose DMPs they commented on 6 or 12 months ago to see what has changed and to update the DMPs together. This also leads to building stronger relationships.

Integrate updating a DMP into research workflow. Investigate common workflows researchers follow and look into opportunities for the integration of DMPs into researchers' workflows. Provide tools or templates that seamlessly align with their existing project planning processes.

Highlight value beyond funding. Shift the focus from a grant requirement to showcasing the intrinsic value of effective data management. Illustrate how well-managed data enhances research integrity, accelerates discoveries, and facilitates future collaborations.

6. Improve the useability of RDM web pages

There is a significant improvement in the way RDM support staff communicates their services to researchers. At a glance, the LibGuide has been updated and follows the natural flow of the research cycle, the calendar of events works and clearly presents the information. The RDM portal clearly shows what is available, it is great to see the members of the team with names and pictures. However, there is still work to do to improve the useability of the information.

- There is a mismatch of information presented on the RDM portal and the faculties pages.
 - Under RDM in your faculty section on the RDM portal, some links lead to no RDM pages or 404 error pages.
 - Some existing Data Stewards are not listed on the RDM portal and faculty pages.
 - RDM-related courses such as “How to write a DMP” are not listed on the RDM portal, but for some reason exist under the courses for PhD students. At the same time, the “Write a data management plan” page on the RDM portal provides various links, with none of those directed to the course sign-up page.
- Some needed information is missing on the web pages:
 - Information about future dates and ways to sign up for some RDM courses is missing, leaving the researchers puzzled about the next steps;
 - Some decision-making tools like data classification and storage finder require additional information to enable researchers to make a decision.
- RDM portal seems to lack hierarchical URL-based navigation. Unlike conventional websites with a hierarchical menu system, the RDM portal navigation doesn't follow a logical tree-like structure. Instead, users access different parts of the site through distinct URLs, creating a

less intuitive navigation experience. This creates confusion and decreases user engagement, presumably adding more work for support staff who are asked basic questions because of it.

The RDM community has gone a long way to achieve improvements in RDM awareness. Yet, the online presence is a baseline that must be kept clean and neat at all times. A well-organised and accessible online presence speaks volumes about the RDM support staff's professionalism and attention to detail. Consistency in content presentation fosters trust and credibility among users. It also stimulates further engagement and meaningful actions done by researchers, which is the next goal of RDM support staff.

Consider working with a user experience designer to improve the aspects above.